

STUDY OF SOCIAL INTEGRATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF RURAL AND URBAN WORKING MOTHERS

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Abstract

The presented paper is intended for analysis and interpretation of data collected to a comparative study of social integration of secondary school students of working mothers from rural and urban areas. Data have been collected from the Kumaun region of Uttarakhand state. The findings of the study reveal that the language, educational status, religion, community, state and caste dimensions of Social Integration among urban and rural secondary school students of working mothers was similar. However, the rural secondary school students of working mothers had higher levels of economic status related social integration than the urban secondary school students of working mothers. The findings revealed that the urban secondary school students of working mothers had more or less similar mean score of social integration as compared with rural secondary school students of working mothers. The mean difference between scores of urban and rural secondary school students of working mothers for Social Integration was found statistically insignificant.

Introduction:

The family is one of the primary groups of society concerned with face-to-face relationship. A child's earliest education is received in his family. The economic status, attitudes and behavioral experiences of parents and family environment all influence the child's behavior and attitudes, both directly and indirectly. In a family the role of the mother in the development of the child is very vital. A child usually spends maximum time with his/her mother. Motherhood confers upon a woman the responsibility of raising a child. It is the result of employment of both husband and wife that family roles of men and women are also changing. It is, therefore, reasonable to expect that the home environment in dual and single earner families will differ. As more and more women are taking up jobs in organized and unorganized

sectors, their children are either left with maids or other family members, whereas, non-working mothers on the contrary have more time to spend with their children, thus there develops a difference in pattern of development among the children of working and non-working mothers as far as their social adjustment with peers, teachers and other members of the society are concerned. On the other hand, this also has a great impact on their social problems and social integration.

The Investigator feels that the findings of the present study will enable us to locate those potential areas in which educational programs for parents can be organized. A large sample of 1000 students were selected for the study, reflected a well representation of rural and urban secondary school students of working and non-working mothers.

Objectives:

- To Study the Social Integration of Secondary School Students of Working Mothers based on their Social Belongingness.

Definition of variables – The variables used are defined as under-

Social Integration- The broadening of the feeling of 'us' (party, group, etc.) in the narrow sense to the feeling of "us" at the societal level. It can be summarized as principles that guide relationships between people and groups in the larger society and how they interact with one another.

Secondary School Students- Secondary school students are students of classes IX and X. They were the students who were passing through the period of adolescence. Along with their physical maturity they develop their personality which was completely based on the family situation.

Working Mothers- Working mothers were those women who work outside the home for a wage or salary besides performing their domestic duties.

Social Belongingness – Secondary school students of working mothers who live in Rural and Urban areas.

Delimitation of the Study

To conduct the study with a large population was not possible so the study was limited to the following-

- The study was delimited only to the Kumaun region of Uttarakhand state to secondary school students, i.e. the students of class IX and X.
- The problem was delimited only to those students whose mother works either in any

government or semi-government sector, working mothers and housewives/non-working mothers only.

- The proposed study was confined to a sample of approximately 1000 secondary school students only.
- Only the social belongingness- rural and urban variable was studied in the study.

Hypotheses-

- There is no significant difference in social integration of secondary school students of working mothers based on their social belongingness.

Research Method-

The current study is meant to explore the social integration of secondary school students of rural and urban working mothers. Therefore, descriptive research design had been employed for the current study. This design was concerned with surveying, describing and investigating the prevailing phenomena or issues, conditions and relationships that exist among target population.

Population

Population is also referred to as Universe in statistics. For the purpose of this study the target population includes secondary school students of Kumaun region from Government, Semi-Government and Public schools in the region.

Sample of the Study

A sample, in other words, could be a smaller representation of the whole (Mugenda and Mugenda, 1999). The present study was descriptive research, based on the normative survey method. Researcher collected responses from 1000 respondents by using simple random sampling. The respondents, i.e., students were selected from Government, Semi-Government and Public schools of three districts of the Kumaun region as per the alternate alphabetical order namely, Bageshwar, Nainital and US Nagar. These districts represented the geography of the state very well since these districts include Hill, Semi-hill and Plains area respectively.

Research Tools

For measuring Social Integration of secondary school students, researcher used the revised version of Social Integration Scale constructed and standardized by Professor (Dr.) Shanti Nayal and Professor (Dr.) G.S. Nayal.

Description and Scoring

The Social Integration tool has 75 items under 7 areas- a) Language, b) Economic Status, c)

Educational Status, **d)** Religion, **e)** Community, **f)** Province, **g)** Caste. The tool description of the social integration tool is as follows:

Table 1.1: Details of Social Integration scale.

S.N.	Areas	No of Item	Total no. of items
1.	Language	1 – 12	12
2.	Economic Status	13 – 24	12
3.	Educational	25 – 34	10
4.	Religion	35 – 44	10
5.	Community/Sect	44 – 55	11
6.	State/Province	56 – 65	10
7.	Caste	66 – 75	10
Total			75

The items were scored on a five-point scale with the following options:

- a)** Strongly Agree, **b)** Agree, **c)** Neutral, **d)** Disagree, **e)** Strongly Disagree
 5 4 3 2 1

The positive items were so stated that if the answer was strongly agree, a score of '5' was given; for agree '4'; for neutral '3'; for disagree '2' and for strongly disagree, a score of '1' was awarded and vice versa for the negative items the scores were awarded '1', '2', '3', '4', and '5'. Therefore, total score on the scale was indicative of social integration whereas the greater the total score on the scale was expressed in terms of higher social integration. The maximum social integration was 375 (75 items \times 5 marks) and the minimum social integration score was 75 (75 items \times 1 mark).

Reliability

The reliability of the social integration scale was calculated by split-half method and found to be 0.90. The test-retest reliability of the scale was estimated to be 0.84. These facts established that the scale is a reliable tool for measuring the social integration of the adolescents.

Statistical Techniques

The parametric statistics i.e. Mean, S.D. and 't' test of significance was used according to the nature of data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 1. To Study the Social Integration of Secondary School Students of Working Mothers based on their Social Belongingness.

Table 1.2: Dimension wise mean, S.D. and *t*-values of social integration of secondary school students of working mothers based on social belongingness.

Dimensions of Social Integration	Social Belongingness	N	Mean	S.D.	<i>t</i> value	Level of Significance
Language Items	Urban	254	38.17	5.26	1.82	N.S.
	Rural	116	39.34	6.68		
Economic Status Items	Urban	254	35.57	5.97	4.30	0.01
	Rural	116	38.58	6.75		
Educational Status Items	Urban	254	27.80	4.74	1.14	N.S.
	Rural	116	27.22	4.24		
Religion wise Items	Urban	254	30.24	5.73	0.69	N.S.
	Rural	116	29.83	4.03		
Community wise Items	Urban	254	33.39	6.57	0.23	N.S.
	Rural	116	33.23	5.82		
State wise Items	Urban	254	30.56	5.73	0.42	N.S.
	Rural	116	30.32	3.88		
Caste wise Items	Urban	254	30.94	5.39	1.48	N.S.
	Rural	116	31.81	4.93		

Summarizing the results of the analysis, it can be inferred that the language, educational status, religion, community, state and caste dimensions of Social Integration among urban and rural secondary school students of working mothers was more or less similar. However, the rural secondary school students of working mothers had higher levels of economic status related social integration than the urban secondary school students of working mothers.

Table 1.3: Mean, S.D. and *t*-value of social integration of secondary school students of working mothers on the basis of their social belongingness.

Social Belongingness	N	Mean	S.D.	<i>t</i> – value	Level of Significance
Urban	254	226.68	31.11	1.11	N.S.
Rural	116	230.33	24.85		

Data presented in Table 1.4 revealed that the urban secondary school students of working mothers had more or less similar mean score of social integration as compared with rural secondary school students of working mothers. The results were clearly depicted by bar graph shown in Figure 4.18. The mean difference between scores of urban and rural secondary school students of working mothers for Social Integration was found statistically insignificant at 0.05 level of significance ($t = 1.11$).

On the basis of these results, the hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in social integration of secondary school students of working mothers based on their social belongingness” was accepted.

Results

- the language, educational status, religion, community wise, state wise, and cast wise dimension of Social Integration of secondary school students of working mothers belonging to rural and urban area was found more or less similar.
- The secondary school students of working mothers from rural area were found higher in economic status dimension than secondary school students of working mothers from urban area.
- The social integration of secondary school students of working mothers was more or less similar on the basis of their social belongingness. The rural and urban secondary school students of working mothers were found similar in their social integration.

Educational Implications

- In dual earner families, parents need to talk to their children to understand their psychological needs and to help them in their studies and choosing their career etc also.
- Women's job should be taken seriously just like man's job. Attitude of acceptance, support, and recognizing her job, to be just like important as the males. This can instil confidence, feeling of self-esteem and self-worth leading to better home adjustment.
- No Partiality should be shown by parents, teachers, community members on any basis. Equal treatment and opportunities should be provided to them.

Bibliography

- Adams, E., and Gold, J. (2009). *Social information processing, moral reasoning, and emotion attributions: Relations with adolescents' reactive and proactive aggression*. *Child Development*, 80, pp. 1739–1755.
- Barua, K., and Barua, J. (1999). *Adjustments Differences of Adolescents in Relation to Maternal Employment*. *Indian Educational Abstract*, 1(1), p. 15.
- Chen, X., and French, D.C. (2008). *Children's social competence in cultural context*. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 59, pp. 591-616.
- Colonnesi, C., Zeegers, M.A., Majdandžić, M., van Steensel, F.J., and Bögels, S.M. (2019). *Fathers' and mothers' early mind-mindedness predicts social competence and behavior problems in childhood*. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 47(9), pp. 1421-1435.
- Ferguson, C. (2008). *Promoting Social Integration*. Report commissioned by the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) for the Expert Group Meeting on Promoting Social Integration, Helsinki, Finland, 8(10).
- Nayal, S. (1990). *Correlates of Social Integration among School Adolescents: social Responsibility, Morality and Self-concept*. Ph.D. Thesis, Kumaun University, Nainital.
- Ruchkin, V., Sukhodolsky, D.G., Vermeiren, R., Koposov, R.A. and Schwab-Stone M. (2006). *Depressive symptoms and associated psychopathology in urban adolescents: a cross-cultural study of three countries*. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 194(2), pp. 106-113.